

Influence of TVET Institutions in Minimizing Challenges Faced by Engineering students in their Attempt to Acquire Requisite Industry Skills in Western Kenya

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Abstract

The Government of Kenya has made tremendous efforts to help young people acquire relevant skills that would enable them fit well in the labour market. For instance, it has resolved to construct and equip new Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions in almost all constituencies in Kenya and provide capitation for all students in those institutions. However, most students specializing in engineering courses still don't pass well in the national exams and when they finally do after repeating classes severally; they still don't perform well in industries or companies that require their skills. Tertiary education is considered one of the key pillars in our socio-economic growth projections. The areas of study were Electrical Engineering, Automotive and Mechanical Engineering, Building Construction and Civil Engineering departments. The objectives of the study were: to identify challenges facing students pursuing Engineering courses at diploma level in Western Kenya, to highlight different strategies TVET institutions can employ to minimize the challenges faced by trainees and to establish the various skills that industries and companies require for them to absorb the unemployed youths in our country. Development Participatory Theory informed the study and descriptive research design was adopted. The targeted population was 14 respondents from which 4 were sampled using Yamane formula. The main sampling technique used was purposive sampling. An interview schedule was used to collect data which was analyzed qualitatively. This study is significant for all stakeholders in TVET institutions. The findings revealed that most students fail to acquire the necessary skills due to lack of enough time for study, lack of enough resources, delayed process of getting government capitation among others. One of the recommendations suggested is that, practical methods of communication should be embraced and funded by the Government and the Non-Governmental Organizations.

Key words: Tertiary, skills, labour market, projections

Introduction

This research paper investigated the influence of TVET institutions in minimizing challenges faced by engineering students in their attempt to acquire requisite industry skills in Western Kenya. The Government of Kenya has made tremendous efforts to help the youths acquire the requisite industry skills that would enable them fit well in the labour market. For instance, there have been constructions of technical institutions in almost all the constituencies in Kenya, equipping these institutions with the needed facilities and resources, employing qualified trainers and providing capitation for each learner. It is expected that graduates from TVET institutions should perform better than their counterparts in other sectors, especially universities where learning is theory based. Despite the efforts made by the government, a good number of youths still don't have the requisite skills and competences needed in the job market. The most affected lot are those students pursuing engineering courses. TVET institutions can play a major role in minimizing the challenges faced by engineering students as they struggle to acquire skills required. Labour Market Intelligence can provide data that guides the graduates on the skills required by industries. Most TVET institutions, for instance have been trying to establish Office of Career Service to guide learners before they select courses, during training and after completing the courses. Tracer studies are also being carried to follow up with students who have left the institutions of learning and are hunting for jobs or have been absorbed in various sectors. We therefore need to re-model the way things are done. Young people need to be involved for them to mobilize and take charge of the situation. It is expected that there is proper coordination between different agencies for purposes of better communication and dissemination of information.

A lot of efforts have been made by the Kenyan Government to ensure that the youths who graduate from universities and colleges acquire relevant skills that would help them get self-employed or join various sectors that offer employment. There is great demand for skilled labour in most sectors of our economy. However, most students specializing in engineering courses do not perform well in the national exams and when they finally do after repeating classes severally; they still don't have the skills required by industries and companies. It means that the supply that is available in the labour market is not relevant for the existing demands.

The purpose of this study was to determine the specific requisite industry skills that are required in Western Kenya and to find out why our youths who go through tertiary institutions still don't have the necessary skills and competences.

Research objectives

The research was guided by the following objectives:

- i. To identify challenges facing students pursuing engineering courses at diploma level in TVET institutions in Western Kenya;
- ii. To highlight different strategies TVET institutions can employ to minimize the challenges faced by trainees;
- iii. To establish the various skills that industries and companies require for them to absorb the unemployed youths in our country.

Theoretical framework

The study employed Development Participatory Theory by Quebral (2007). This model stresses the importance of cultural identity of local communities and of democratization and participation at all levels. The model further states that, in order to share information, knowledge, trust, commitment and the right attitude to the process of development, participation is very important in any decision making. The model calls for change of attitude, for overcoming stereotype thinking, promoting and understanding the diversity and popularity with full respect for dignity and equality. Taken as it is, it means that participatory communication involves all people in any setting irrespective of their condition, living standards, level of education among other aspects. It stresses reciprocal collaboration throughout all levels of participation. However, the role of development specialists, planners, individual leaders and the rest must still be upheld. It calls for active participation in effective communication by all stake holders who should act from the start of any project to the implementation stage. The model can therefore be applied where active participation in communication is used as a strategy for acquiring new skills.

Literature Review

Challenges facing students pursuing engineering courses

According to Boudah (2010), there are many challenges facing engineering students, including exam stress, balancing life studies, problems with management or pressure from tutors, procrastination, exhaustion and isolation. He gives different suggestions to help solve these problems including, setting achievable goals, time management, making schedules, taking a break, managing both social life and studies, staying healthy and getting enough sleep among others.

Skills required industries

Boudah (2010) has investigated and come up with different skills that may be required in industry. Some of the main skills that one may need in the manufacturing industry include: Excellent Communication Skills which are essential in all areas of work, the ability to work as part of a team, that is, one should be able to work well alongside others. One can also demonstrate leadership skills and potential by taking the initiative and supporting colleagues. It is also necessary for one to develop a strong work ethic and always be able to put in 100% at work, have time management skills, pay attention to details, think critically, have aptitude for technology and equipment in order to gain confidence with the relevant technology and equipment.

Development Participatory communication

The Practice of Development communication began in the 1940s, but widespread application came about after World War II. The advent of communication sciences in the 1950s included recognition of the field as an academic discipline, led by Rogers & Shoemaker (1971: 3). Both Childers and Quebral, (1973) stressed that Development Communication includes all means of communication, ranging from mass media to interpersonal contact. According to Quebral (1973), the most important feature of Philippines-style development communications is that the government is the 'chief designer and administrator of the master (development) plan wherein, participatory communication, in this system then is purposive, persuasive, goal-directed, audience-oriented, and interventionist by nature'.

Bessette (2006) defined Participatory communication as a 'planned and systematic application of communication resources, channels, approaches and strategies to support the goals of socio-

economic, political and cultural development. According to Masilela (1991), participation translates into individuals being active in development programmes and processes; they contribute ideas, take initiative and articulate their needs and their problems, while asserting their autonomy.

The emerging issues in communication emphasize the use of practical application processes and technologies in achieving positive and measurable development outcomes. Globally and even locally, the emerging issues also include use of information communication technology (ICT), the internet, which incorporates the use of social media including face book, whatsApp, twitter and many other forms of social media. Also, on trade related issues, the emerging issues include the discussions on e-commerce and e-governance. E-commerce refers to the commercial transaction conducted electronically on the internet. It actually involves buying and selling online. It uses communication technology such as mobile commerce, electronic transfer among others. E-commerce has been in existence for some years now but it keeps incorporating many changes as it advances. It falls under an emerging issue in communication because we use it to advance and empower ourselves economically. We can now use e-commerce to purchase things like vehicles, furniture and many others. The challenges that affect e-commerce include conning, fraud, sanctions from governments, high taxation on imported goods, harking and many others. We also have e-governance as an emerging issue. E-governance refers to the application of ICT for delivering government services, exchanging of information, communication transactions, integration of various systems and services between government and clients. It also uses social media for social change, leading to behavioral change. Also the emergence of global health and environmental issues and communication styles, consumption of materials and cultural processes that have helped to bring globalization of our world have been avenues for participatory communication that lead to transformation. In general, technology and participatory communication have greatly impacted on our social, economic, political and even educational lives.

Methodology

The present research used descriptive research design and the targeted population was 14 respondents from each academic department. Out of these, 4 were sampled using Yamane formula. The main sampling technique that was used was purposive sampling. Interview schedule was used to collect data from the sampled respondents. Names of the respondents were not used for purposes

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of confidentiality. Instead abbreviations were used for participants' anonymity. Verbatim quotations from interviews were transcribed and analyzed qualitatively.

Results and Discussion.

This section deals with the results and discussion of the findings of the study. The information given follows the stated objectives. In the interviews carried out, the respondents were represented as Heads of Electrical Engineering (EE), Automotive and Mechanical Engineering (AMB), Building and Construction (BC) and Civil Engineering (CE).

Challenges facing students pursuing Engineering Courses at Diploma level.

The qualitative interviews carried out from HODs revealed that most engineering students fail to acquire the necessary skills due to lack of enough time for studies. This is majorly due to too much time taken by scheduled external exams, including KNEC, KANEB, NITA among others. KNEC, for example, takes over three months of academic year, that is, March, July and November. This information was supported by a respondent's response as follows:

Each term is made up of 3 months but KNEC exams take over 1 month just before the holidays begin. Lecturers also go for marking during the holidays hence no learning takes place after the external exams, meaning, around 6 months go without much interaction between the trainers and trainees.

There is also lack of necessary facilities and resources like enough computers, big halls for common courses, internet connectivity and many others. Shortage of personnel, especially specialists in the field of engineering is also a thorn in the flesh. TVET institutions lack capacity to impart the necessary skills needed in the job market. This was supported by the following responses:

Lack of engineering tools and equipment is a major impediment to good performance in TVET institutions. For instance, Electrical Engineering course requires a lot of electrical gadgets which most administrators do not want to purchase.

Automotive and Mechanical Engineering courses also require expensive resources and facilities including vehicles to be used during practical classes, though most institutions use grounded vehicles.

Most TVET trainees sometimes miss lessons due to delayed process of getting government capitation. As much as the government has made a lot of efforts to ensure each learner in the TVET institutions gets capitation, the process is sometimes too slow to the extent that some trainees are chased away during internal exams because of failure to produce exam cards which are only given to those who have cleared fees in one particular term. The following excerpt illustrates the same:

A good number of trainees are grappling with financial challenges and are not able to pay fees in good time or meet their other obligations like up keep, accommodation expenses among others. Most of the time they are queuing at the finance office, registrar's office or at the point of eating for 'pay as you eat', hence a lot of time is wasted.

Strict rules should be adhered to by all stake holders. Trainees should attend classes as scheduled and the number of hours should be set and any that falls below the set minimum attendance target should be punished by being given lower grades or forced to repeat a course. Trainers should cover their lessons fully and students can easily report cases of missed lessons. Administrators should ensure enough resources and facilities are availed whenever requisitions are made.

Skills that industries and companies require for them to absorb the unemployed youths in our country

The Participatory Communication can help in disseminating information to the youths who should acquire the right skills. This model is relevant in TVET institutions where learning should involve practical skills. Communication is vital to the learners. Practical Communication or Participatory Communication helps young people acquire the right skills. The following responses can support the information:

Practical lessons should be emphasized instead of theoretical ones. 80% to 90% of lesson attendance should be used for practical skills in all TVET institutions.

TVET institutions should have collaboration with industries which should be accommodating the majority of their students. They shouldn't emphasize on the minimum number of students being attached or who go for internship or are volunteering to work in their organizations.

All TVET institutions should establish Office of Career Service in order to guide trainees before they register for a course, during the learning process and after they leave. This can help them select courses they can be comfortable with.

Tracer studies should be carried out to help TVET alumni get information on which industries are looking for which skills in the labour market.

9 Findings

- i. The findings revealed that most engineering students fail to acquire the necessary skills due to lack of enough time for studies.
- ii. There is lack of necessary facilities and resources like enough computers, big halls for common courses, internet connectivity and shortage of personnel, especially specialists in the field of engineering.
- iii. TVET trainees sometimes miss lessons due to delayed process of getting government capitation
- iv. The findings also revealed that, there are challenges faced by TVET institutions as a result of external exams like KNEC, KASNEB, NITA and other examining bodies.
- v. TVET institutions lack capacity to impart the necessary skills needed in the job market.
- vi. TVET institutions can play a vital role in coming up with innovative responses
- vii. The Participatory Communication can help in disseminating information to the youths who should acquire the right skills.
- viii. TVET institutions can employ different strategies to minimize the challenges faced by young people pursuing engineering courses.
- ix. All TVET institutions should establish Office of Career Service in order to guide students on career choices, before, during and after training.
- x. Tracer studies should be carried out to help youths get information on the labour market issues, even after they have left their institutions of learning.

Conclusion

Journal of Technology & Socio - Economic Development, 12(1):231-240, 2024

This research paper investigated the influence of TVET institutions in minimizing challenges faced by engineering students in their attempt to acquire requisite industry skills in Western Kenya. The study has highlighted the different challenges that affect the education sector, especially the TVET institutions and the various strategies that can be used to overcome some of the challenges. The role of stakeholders including the Ministry of Education, the managers, the trainers and even the trainees has been expressed.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommended the following:

1. Practical methods of communication should be embraced and funded by the Government and the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO).
2. Technology should be used as an important tool in the communication process if we have to achieve the set development goals.
3. Participatory communication as an approach to communication should be considered if the stake holders have to enhance behavioral change.
4. The TVET institutions also need to engage the trainers by assigning them responsibility of identifying and reaching out to youths with different skills in their locality and helping them to improve those skills through the use of modern machines which are available in most TVET institutions.
5. The youths should learn to create apps and design websites for purposes of scanning documents, imparting knowledge and skills needed.
6. TVET institutions should also increase internet connectivity to allow trainees employ mentorship and training mechanism that can help them acquire the needed skills.
7. The stake holders in education sector need to ensure capitation for TVET students are disbursed in good time.
8. Office of Career Service should be established in all TVET institutions.
9. Tracer studies should be carried out to follow up with different Institutions' Alumni to know whether they are placed in different sectors of the economy as employees or employers.

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